

VIT
NATIONAL CONFERENCE

Vidyalankar Institute of Technology

Wadala (E), Mumbai -400037

VIT

Vidyalankar
Institute of
Technology
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**National Conference
on**

"Innovations in Electronics & Information Technology"

This is to certify that

Jayen Modi

Presented a paper on

"Radio Frequency Identification"

at the National Conference,

"Innovations in Electronics & Information Technology" organized by
Vidyalankar Institute of Technology, Wadala, Mumbai-37 on October 05-06, 2009.

Prof. Shrikant Velankar
Convener, IEIT 2009

Dr. Prashant Sonare
Principal, VIT